

Friedel-Craft Reaction of α -(+) Acid Halide

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Few optically active unsymmetrical aromatic ketones were reported in the literature. With a view of study the effect of different types of alkyl substituents on the optical activity the present study has been undertaken, to prepare¹ optically active unsymmetrical aromatic ketones of the type

by Friedel-Craft reaction. α -(+)-2-methyl valeryl chloride was condensed with different types of aromatic hydrocarbons in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The optical rotations of these ketones have been measured and recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I

Optically active unsymmetrical ketones of the type $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\overset{\text{CH}_3}{\underset{|}{\text{C}}}\text{CH}_2\text{CO.A/r}$

Aryl form.	Sp. Rotation (1 = 1) [α] _D ²⁰	Density <i>d</i> ₄ ²⁰	Refractive index. <i>n</i> _D ²⁰	b.p./15-20/mm °C	Yield %
Benzene	+7.58	1.032	1.532	135—145	70.0
Toluene	+7.60	1.030	1.535	140—145	66.0
<i>m</i> -Xylene	+7.75	1.029	1.539	140—145	55.0
<i>p</i> -Cymene	+7.46	1.027	1.545	145—148	48.0
Chlorobenzene	+7.40	1.161	1.551	125—132	53.0
Bromobenzene	+7.12	1.185	1.562	130—140	50.0
Ethylbenzene	+5.62	1.034	1.546	175—185	50.0
Anisole	+7.76	1.091	1.544	155—162	48.0
Phenetole	+7.06	0.9986	1.533	175—185	45.0

All the compounds described gave correct C, H-Analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -(+)-2-methyl valeric acid: The fusel oil contains α -(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol was distilled at 128–130° using a 16 cm. long fractionating column whereby pure α -(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol was obtained.

$$[(\alpha)_D^{30} - 4.69 (l = 1), d_4^{30} 0.8279, n^{30} 1.45]$$

α -(+)-1-bromo-2-methyl butane was obtained by the bromination of α -(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol (320 gms.) with red phosphorus (20.71 gms) and liquid bromine (266.6 gms.). The resulting α -(+)-1-bromo-2-methyl butane was distilled at 116–118°.

$$[(\alpha)_D^{30} + 1.52 (l = 1), d_4^{30} 1.258, n^{30} 1.4580].$$

α -(+)-1-bromo-2-methyl butane (151.0 gms., 1 mole) prepared as above in ether (250 ml) was added during 3 hr. to a flask containing dry magnesium (24.32 gms., 1 mole) and ether (250 ml). The Grignard complex prepared as above, was refluxed for 1 hr. and dry carbon dioxide gas was passed through it at -5 to 0° for 2 hr. It was decomposed by ammonium chloride solution (10%), extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (2*N*). The α -(+)-2-methyl valeric acid was obtained by acidifying the sodium salt with hydrochloric acid (conc.), extracted with ether, and on evaporation of the solvent the residual α -(+)-2-methyl valeric acid was obtained which was dried by anhy. magnesium sulphate and distilled at 97 to 100°/15 mm.

$$[(\alpha)_D^{30} + 3.76 (l = 1), d_4^{30} 0.9636, n^{30} 1.4410, \text{Yield } 70 \text{ gms. } 60.34\%]$$

α -(+)-2-methyl valeryl chloride: α -(+)-2-methyl valeric acid (116 gm., 1 mole) and thionyl chloride (180 gms., 1.5*M*) were refluxed on water bath for 1 hr. The excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off and the residual α -(+)-2-methyl valeryl chloride was distilled at 140 to 145°.

$$[(\alpha)_D^{30} + 2.95 (l = 1), d_4^{30} 0.9428, n^{30} 1.4350. \text{Yield } 95 \text{ gms. } 70\%].$$

Aryl ketones: The reaction was carried out as usual by the interaction of α -(+)-2-methyl valeryl chloride (0.34*M*) and aromatic hydrocarbons (1.03*M*) using anhy. aluminium chloride (40 gms.). The compounds prepared are listed in Table 1.

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